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BETWEEN DUTY AND HEART: CHALLENGES AND COPING STRATEGIES OF ADULT CHILDREN CARING FOR AGING PARENTS

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study explored the lived experiences of adult children as caregivers for their aging parents in Abuyog, Leyte. Grounded in the Filial Care Theory and Resilience Theory, it delved into adult children's motivations, challenges, coping strategies, and realizations in providing care for their aging parents. Using a phenomenological approach, it employed a semi-structured interview on eight participants.

The findings show participants' varied motivations in providing care for their aging parents such as the desire to repay the parents' sacrifices and experiencing a sense of duty and gratitude. Additionally, it revealed that participants struggle with emotional and psychological strain, financial difficulties, role strain, and issues in communication but rely on self-relaxation, social and familial support, spiritual faith, and reframing their role positively as coping strategies. It also delved on how the participants' experience affected their perceptions on aging, providing insights and realizations.

Moreover, this study contributes to the limited study on adult children as caregivers for their aging parents and highlights the need to establish support programs and workshops to relieve caregiver burden and aid them in providing care to their aging parents.

Keywords: caregiving, adult children, debt of gratitude, filial responsibility, repay

INTRODUCTION

Adult children as caregivers for aging parents is a practice commonly observed in Asia, including the Philippines. This act of caregiving is rooted in filial responsibility, the obligation that adult children feel to provide care and support to their parents (Wakui & Cheng, 2016). This caregiving role borne of filial responsibility encompasses but is not limited to having shared living arrangements, and providing support ranging from physical, emotional, and financial help (Wakui & Cheng, 2016).

The decision for adult children to provide care for their aging parents is influenced by multiple factors, one is having a sense of responsibility to repay their parents as they feel a sense of "utang na loob" or debt of gratitude (Medina & Medina, 2023) while a study by Uy (2023) found that providing care for parents is seen as a way to maintain family honor and avoid shame or kahihyan. This practice is recognized and encouraged as observed in the 1987 Constitution of the Philippines Article XV Section 4 which encourages the family to care for its elderly members. Recently, the Parents Welfare Act of 2025 was proposed to further encourage filial responsibility and penalize those who fail to provide for their aging parents (Senate of the Philippines, 2025).

However, a study of Joya et al. (2024) revealed that most Filipinos are not prepared for this responsibility. Caregivers reportedly experienced caregiver burden as they encountered constraints while providing care (Liu et al., 2020) and with the lack of institutional support, these caregivers are faced with emotional stress and financial burden (Ng & Indran, 2021). Additionally, a study by

Pashazade et al. (2024) found adult children who are simultaneously responsible for their own children and aging parents similarly face challenges.

While previous research has explored filial responsibility and caregiving, the lived experiences and perspective of adult children as caregivers for their aging parents has been largely unexplored. As such, there remains a notable gap in the literature concerning the experiences of these adult children providing caregiving support.

This study therefore addresses its gap by exploring the lived experiences of adult children who serve as caregivers for their aging parents. It aims to understand how these individuals navigate their caregiving roles, their challenges, and how their experiences shaped them. By understanding their experiences, certain steps can be taken to mitigate the challenges they experience and increase empathy towards their situation.

Statement of the Problem

This study seeks to explore the lived experiences of adult children as caregivers for their aging parents. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do the participants interpret and make sense of their caregiving roles within the context of Filipino culture and values?
2. What challenges do the participants face in the caregiving journey?
3. What are the challenges encountered by the participants in communicating with their aging parents?
4. How do the participants cope and adapt to these challenges?
5. In what ways has the caregiving experience influenced the participants' personal identity and family relationships?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design This study employed a phenomenological research design to explore the experiences of adult children as caregivers for their aging parents. Phenomenology, as defined by Neubauer et al. (2019), is a qualitative approach that seeks to understand lived experiences from the perspectives of those who have directly undergone them, making it an appropriate methodology for this study. By using this design, the research was able to provide a rich, nuanced understanding of the participants' caregiving experiences, capturing both the complexities and emotional dimensions involved in supporting their elderly parents.

Research Instrument This study utilized a semi-structured interview as the main data collection method. This encouraged more in-depth discussion of topics related to the study. The researchers also made use of audio recording to record data for analysis.

Validation of Research Instrument To ensure the validity of the research instrument, it was rigorously examined by the research advisor, ensuring the interview questions were appropriate and aligned with the research objectives.

Locale of the Study This study was conducted in Abuyog, Leyte, Philippines. This location was selected for its diverse population, allowing for a broad and rich collection of data, and for its ease of access.

Participant Selection and Sampling Participants of the study were selected using the snowball sampling method following the specific criteria: adult children of any gender who serves as the primary caregiver of their aging parents. To ensure the quality of the data, selected participants must have a minimum of 6 months experience in providing firsthand care to their aging parents.

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Characteristics of the Participants

Participant's Code	Sex	Civil Status	Duration of Caregiving Experience
P1	Female	Married	5 years
P2	Male	Married	3 years
P3	Male	Married	2 years
P4	Female	Married	6 years
P5	Female	Single	4 years
P6	Female	Single	5 years
P7	Female	Married	2 years
P8	Male	Married	3 years

Data Analysis The data collected from the participants were examined using thematic analysis. This included creating a full transcript of the interviews, careful analysis of each transcript to further understand the content and coding of significant statements which were then grouped and further categorized into identified themes. Each theme was then carefully analyzed to ensure in-depth understanding, allowing for creation of exhaustive description and discussion of the experiences of adult children as caregivers of aging parents.

Data Gathering Procedure The data gathering procedure involved a short informational briefing wherein the participants were informed of their role and were provided with a concise explanation regarding the research's objective. After signing the Consent Form, participants then began their individual interviews. The collected data were then analyzed using thematic analysis.

Ethical Considerations Participants were duly informed of their role before participating in the interviews. Interviews were conducted individually to ensure their privacy and the data collected were handled only by the researchers to protect the participants' identity. All due procedures were followed in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Research Reflexivity According to Olmos-Vega et al. (2022), reflexivity is having awareness of one's own assumptions, belief, judgement systems, and critically examining how these influence the research process. To ensure research reflexivity, the researchers wrote a personal journal throughout the research process to keep track of their own perceptions and possible biases, thus ensuring that the findings were objective and not affected by their personal opinions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the thorough examination of the data, the following themes emerged

Reciprocity and Responsibility: Motivations in Caregiving

This theme highlights how the decision to provide care for aging parents is influenced by multiple factors. Intergenerational Solidarity Theory (Bengston & Roberts, 1991) introduced normative solidarity, which focuses on the perceived duty adult children feels to provide care for their parents due to generational beliefs and expectations. This aligns with Participant 6's experience as she stated: "*Amo man gud it ginbubuhat nganhi haat. Pagnalagas tat mga ginikanan, atun hira ariglarun pareho han pag areglar nat mga ginikanan han ira ginikanan dati.*" ("It's just what's done here. When our parents get older, we take care of them, like how they took care of their parents before.") while Participant 4 added "*Makayakan gad gihap nga parte nak rason nga gin alagaan hira kay amo*

man an ginbubuhat nganhi ha at lugar." ("I can say that part of the reason I'm taking care of them is because it's the norm here.")

On the other hand, other participants shared that they felt a sense of gratitude to their parents and a natural obligation to repay them for their sacrifices. This was evident in Participant 1 who said "*Natural ra nga atimon nato atong ginikanan kay mao man pud ilang gibuhat nato sauna.*" ("It's natural for us to take care of our parents as repayment for everything they've done for us".) Participant 2 echoed that sentiment when he said "*Natural na gud sa atun nga mag give back ha tanan nga mga sakripisyo hit at mga ginikanan.*" ("It's natural for us to give back to our parents after all their sacrifices for us.") This supports the study of Charenkova (2023) which claimed that an adult child's decision to provide care for their aging parents is influenced by a desire to repay them for their sacrifices.

The results indicate that adult children's motivations for caring for aging parents align with Bedford and Yeh's (2019) Dual Filial Piety Model, which distinguishes between Reciprocal Filial Piety—care motivated by gratitude and emotional connection—and Authoritarian Filial Piety—care driven by obedience and maintaining family honor.

Strain and Sacrifice: Challenges in Caregiving

Participants shared a range of challenges when caring for their aging parents, which affected their ability to provide care.

Emotional and Psychological Strain.

Participant 6 noted: "*Makuri talaga ihinumdum tanan nga responsibilidad ko ha iya pareho hit pagtigaman iya mga medisina. Mas napakuri pa kay masakit makit an ak nanay nga di na makusog ngan nagkukuri.*" ("It's hard to remember all the responsibilities I have for her like monitoring her medicine. What's even harder is seeing my mother no longer strong and having difficulties.")

Financial and Resource Pressure.

Participant 3 best stated: "*Makuri na gud kay kulang man tak suweldo para panbayad ha tanan nga baraydan, it medisina pagkaon, ngan it pan check-up.*" ("It's difficult because my salary isn't enough to cover all expenses like medicine, food, and check-ups.")

Time and Role Conflict.

Participants had trouble balancing their life with their caregiving role. Participant 2 best reflected this with the statement: "*Naapektuhan gad tak personal labi na sit akon trabaho kay danay matawag tak asawa na uli la anay kay mapabulig siya kan tatay o danay maka absent ako tak trabaho kay uupdan pagpa check-up.*" ("It does affect my personal life, especially my work as sometimes my wife asks me to come home to help my father. Sometimes I have to be absent since I need to accompany him to a check-up.") Participant 3 also stated: "*Wa na gyud panahon para ha iba, bisan ha sarili kay pirmi man ada atensiyon ha ira. Di na ak nakalakat lakat upod sangkay, pirmi nala adi ha balay nag alaga.*" ("I really don't have time for anything else even myself because I need to focus all my attention to them. I can't go out with my friends since I'm always at home providing care.")

These statements align with Liu et al.'s (2020) findings that caregivers often encounter multiple challenges resulting in caregiver burden. Additionally, it supports the Role Strain Theory (Goode, 1960), which explains that role strain arises when an individual struggles to meet the demands of various social roles.

Voices in Conflict: Issues in Communication

Participants shared that they encountered difficulties in communicating with their parents. Participant 7 expressed her difficulties as her parent experienced hearing loss: "*Di na man nakabati ha ak. Talagsa kay kadamo damuan ko dapat iyakan it usa la ka hinitabo tas nasina pa hiya kay*

nayakan hiya nga ginsisimpli ko nga duro, bagan ginbaby hiya. May ada gud panahon nga nasumhan ak amo di kami nagkaka istoryaha hin tuhay. ("He can't really hear me properly now. Sometimes I have to repeat things repeatedly and then he gets mad because I'm simplifying things too much, as though I'm babying him. There are times I get frustrated, and it leads to us not communicating properly.") Participant 2 also shared that he had trouble in communication as his father resisted to listen, especially when he gave advice or reminders: *"Kun ipahinumdom ko ha iya an iya medisina, nasina ha ak ngan di namati. Nayakan nga gintrato ko hira nga began bata."* ("When I remind him of his medicine, he gets mad and doesn't listen. He says I'm treating him like a child.")

These statements align with the Communication Accommodation Theory (Giles, 2008) which reflects on how over-accommodation can be perceived negatively, becoming a barrier for communication.

Resilience and Strength: Coping Mechanisms

Participants shared a range of strategies they used to manage stress and overcome challenges. For some participants, self-relaxation was their way to cope. Participant 5 especially stated: *"Para di gud kapuyon hin duro, nag relax ak hin usa la ak kun nakaturog hiya. Talagsa kay nagbasa hin libro o nanmati hin mga kanta."* ("To avoid burnout, I relax by myself while he's sleeping. Sometimes I read a book or listen to music.") Other participants thought of their affection and gratitude towards their parents. Participant 2 highlighted this most clearly: *"It makita ko la tak tatay na nangisi ug nakita nakon na mulaban pa gud siya amo tak rason para magpadayun pa."* ("Seeing my father smiling and fighting is my reason to keep going.")

In addition, some participants coped by relying on social and family support. Participant 7 especially said: *"Amo gud mag bonding kami tak pamilya kun may oras ngan talagsa kay nangaro ak bulig ha ak mga sangkay ngan mga kasilingan."* ("That's why my family and I bond together whenever we have time. Sometimes I also ask for help from my friends and neighbors.")

Having faith also emerged as one of the coping mechanisms, with Participant 3 stating: *"Mayda la ak tiwala ha Ginoo nga buligan kami. Nasimba gihap ak pirmi."* ("I just have trust in God that He'll help us. We also attend the mass.")

Participants used different coping strategies such as self-relaxation, focusing on positive emotions and gratitude felt towards their parents, relying on social and familial support, and having spiritual faith to recover from the challenges they encountered, showing their strength and resilience. This aligns with the Resilience Theory, which emphasizes an individual's ability to thrive despite adversity and stressful situations (Moore, 2019).

Reflections and Realizations: Insights in Caregiving

Participants shared that despite the challenges, their experience allowed them to feel a sense of emotional fulfillment and has affected their perceptions on aging. For some participants, caregiving became a way to express their gratitude and love towards their parents. This is best expressed by Participant 6: *"Ha luyo hit akon kapoy kay proud ak nga akon nahatagan hin dignidad nak Nanay. Tungod hini kay naipakita ko an ak kagugma ha iya."* ("Behind my exhaustion I feel proud that I gave my mother dignity. Because of this I was able to show my love for her.") Participant 3 shared similar sentiments with his statement: *"Bisan gaano kakuri maupay ha pakiramdam nga makabalik ak ha ira katapos han tanan nga ira ginbuhat para ha ak."* ("No matter how hard it is, it feels good to give back to them after everything they did for me.") Participant 7 also reflected on her realizations: *"Narealize ko nga it responsibilidad ha pamilya kay di pabigat, pagpakita ini hin paghigugma tikang*

ha usa ka henerasyon tikadto ha sunod." ("I realized that family responsibility is not a burden, it's a showing of love from one generation to another.")

Participants also expressed their expectations for their own future. Others expressed their hope that their children would provide the same care for them. Participant 1 particularly expressed: "*Kung muabot ang panahon, hinaot nga ang akong anak muhatag pud ug same nga gugma.*" ("If the time comes, I hope my children would give the same love to me.") Other participants stated the same feelings though some expressed that they did not want their children to feel burdened. This is best seen in Participant 7's statement: "*Naasa gad ak nga alagaan gihap ak tak anak pero gusto ko nga mabuhì hira hin waray pabigat. Nadiri ak nga magkuri hira.*" ("I hope that I would be taken care of by my child, but I want them to live without any burden. I don't want them to suffer.")

These statements of reciprocating parents' care align with the Filial Piety Theory (Bedford & Yeh, 2003) particularly on the concept of reciprocal filial piety, in which adult children provide care for their parents out of genuine affection and gratitude. It also supports the study of Pysklywec et al. (2020) regarding the participants' personal growth as they reflected on their circumstances. This shows that to the participants, caregiving was a meaningful role that strengthened their bonds and provided them with an opportunity to provide for their parents out of affection and gratitude.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Adult children's decisions to provide care for their aging parents were influenced by cultural and social expectations and a sense of reciprocity due to gratitude and affection.
2. Adult children caregivers faced challenges such as emotional and psychological strain, financial and resource pressure, time and role conflict, and some issues in communication.
3. To manage the challenges they encountered, the participants engage in multiple coping mechanisms such as self-relaxation, reframing their mindset positively, relying on social and familial support, and having spiritual faith.
4. Participants experienced emotional fulfillment and viewed caregiving as an expression of love and gratitude towards their parents. Moreover, their experience affected their own expectations for their future.

Based on the conclusions, the researchers recommend establishing support programs for adult children caregivers to address their emotional, psychological, and role strain. Institutions should collaborate with these caregivers to provide adequate support that could reduce the load caregivers face significantly. In addition, healthcare institutions could host workshops or seminars to discuss how to handle other barriers caregivers encounter such as their communication barriers or other challenges.

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